

Which factors have a greater impact on review time? — A case study of Nature Communication

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Introduction

Peer review is a process in which reviewers assess the quality of research work. It plays a crucial role in scientific writing and publishing processes. Currently, as more and more academic journals choose to open the corpus of peer review, there is an increasing study about how to improve the accuracy and efficiency of peer review. Mining aspect sentiment of peer review can help authors improve the quality of their manuscripts, thus improving the efficiency of peer review. Liang et al. (2022) examined the relationship between paper novelty and paper processing time based on the journal paper collected by PubMed. They found that the stronger the paper novelty, the longer the processing time. However, they did not mine the fine-grained aspects in peer review to study which aspects can more affect review time. Focusing on these aspects when authors revise their papers will help improve the efficiency of peer review. We construct a corpus of peer review annotated with aspect sentiment for classification model. Then we use the classification model to classify the unannotated corpus. Finally, we analyse the correlation between the review aspect sentiment and review time.

Methodology

The framework of this paper is shown in figure 1. It mainly includes aspect sentiment annotation and aspect sentiment classification.

Figure 1. The framework of this study

Data collection

We use peer review files in *Nature Communications*¹ (NC) as a corpus. NC is a multidisciplinary journal with 5 first-level disciplines and 71 second-level disciplines. We collect the peer review files and review time information of articles in NC. The collected NC journal papers were published from 2016 to 2020, and 41,373 peer review files were obtained. The frequency of peer reviews in the NC's first-level disciplines is shown in table 1 respectively.

Table 1. Distribution of NC Peer Reviews

First-level disciplines	# (Peer reviews)
Biological sciences	21,683
Earth and environmental sciences	2,588
Health Sciences	6,090
Physical sciences	10,180
Scientific community and society	832
Total	41,373

Aspect sentiment annotation of peer review

Han et al. (2022) extracted fine-grained aspects of peer review in NC using double propagation algorithm. They identified 11 aspect clusters through affinity propagation algorithm. Based on their study, we randomly selected 5,000 review sentences containing aspects in the above aspect clusters to manually annotate the sentiment polarity at the aspect level. We divide sentiment polarity into three categories: positive, negative and neutral. Two annotators annotate each review sentence. We evaluate the consistency of each two annotators, and the values are 0.62, 0.68, and 0.62. For the inconsistent review sentences annotated by two annotators, the third annotator check and provide the final annotate.

Sentiment classification model for review aspect

We use annotated corpus to train and test the LCF-BERT model proposed by Zeng et al. (2019). This model uses local context focus (LCF) and semantic relative distance (SeRD) to determine whether the context word is the local context of a specific aspect. And focuses on the local context by calculating the Context Dynamic Mask (CDM) and the Context features Dynamic Weighted (CDW) based on SeRD.

¹ <https://www.nature.com/ncomms/>

Correlation analysis between review aspect sentiment and review time

We analyse the correlation between the review aspect sentiment and review time. First, we use the sentiment score to express the review sentiment quantitatively, and the calculation formula is as follows:

$$S = \frac{N_p - N_{ng}}{N_p + N_{ng} + N_{nu}} \quad (1)$$

Where, N_p is the number of positive sentiments, N_{ng} is the number of negative sentiments, N_{nu} is the number of neutral sentiments. Then, we separately calculate the sentiment score of each aspect cluster and the whole review for each peer review. Besides, we calculate the time difference from when the journal receives the paper to when the paper passes the review to express the review time quantitatively. After that, we use the Pearson correlation coefficient to conduct a bivariate analysis on sentiment score and review time.

Results

Result of aspect sentiment classification

We split the annotation data into a training set and a test set in an 80:20 ratio. The accuracy of the LCF-BERT model for our dataset is 82.72%. And the example result of aspect sentiment classification is shown in Table 2. Han et al. (2022) identified the aspect clusters, including *Problem definition/Idea*, *Conclusions/Discussions*, *Tables/Figures*, *Methodology/Model*, etc. The sentiment refers to the aspect in the review sentence.

Table 2. Example result of aspect sentiment

Cluster	Aspect	Sentiment	Sentence
Conclusions/Discussions	conclusions	negative	However, the conclusions are not exciting or particularly novel.
Methodology/Model	technique	neutral	Author used radical polymerization technique to prepare copolymer.
Methodology/Model	approach	positive	This is an interesting approach in setting a baseline of which taxa are present.

Result of correlation analysis between review aspect sentiment and review time

Correlation analysis on review aspect sentiment and review time for five first-level disciplines are investigated, respectively. For lack of space, only the result of Biological Sciences (BS) is shown in Table 3. The results of the other four first-level disciplines are basically consistent with BS. At the review level, sentiment is negatively correlated with the review time. It indicates the worse the review sentiment, the longer the review time of the article. For BS, clusters such as *Evaluation/Result*, *Experiments/Operations*,

Impact/Research value, *Conclusions/Discussions*, and *Tables/Figures* strongly correlate with review time. These clusters are more likely to lead to a longer review time. However, cluster *Structure/Language* has a relatively weak correlation with review time. This is because revising a paper about structure and language usually takes less time.

Table 3. Result of correlation analysis (take Biological Science as an example)

Cluster	Correlation coefficient
Problem definition/Idea	-0.06**
Data/Datasets	-0.073**
Tables/Figures	-0.093**
Methodology/Model	-0.076**
Experiments/Operations	-0.098**
Conclusions/Discussions	-0.094**
Index/Parameters	-0.06**
Evaluation/Result	-0.107**
Structure/Language	-0.034**
Impact/Research value	-0.098**
Comparison/Correlation	-0.079**
Review	-0.101**

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Conclusion

This paper analyses the correlation between the review aspect sentiment and review time. Aspect clusters such as *Evaluation/Result*, *Tables/Figures*, *Impact/Research value*, and *Experiments/Operations* have a greater impact on the length of review time. Therefore, authors should consider these aspects when revising and optimizing their papers. However, the length of review time is also affected by many other factors. In the future, we will include control variables such as the number of authors, the length of the paper, discipline breadth, etc.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 72074113).

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